

SHORE: EmpOweR Students as the agents of cHange

Melotti, Luca (1); Currò, Sarah (1); Graïc, Jean-Marie (1); Ionaşcu, Andreea (2); Paiu, Marian (2)

- 1. Department of Comparative Biomedicine and Food Science, University of Padua, Legnaro (Padova), Italy*
- 2. Mare Nostrum NGO, Constanța, Romania*

The escalating threats to the health of the marine environment, stemming from human activities, pose and will continue to pose a significant impact on the well-being of European citizens. Consequently, it is imperative to empower the public, particularly the youth, with accurate knowledge about the marine ecosystem, its significance, their individual contributions to its well-being, and reciprocal effects on their lives. Recognizing the pivotal role of children as agents of change, ocean literacy campaigns should seamlessly integrate dissemination initiatives into school curricula, fostering water literate citizens for conservation. EmpOweR Students as the agents of cHange (SHORE) is a collaborative European project funded under European Union's Mission Ocean, committed to increase ocean literacy in schools by engaging students and educators to fulfill its objectives through school community activities. The project specifically targets primary and secondary schools, recruiting them to the European Blue School network (8-14 years old). It provides funding of up to €10,000 for water literacy projects through three Open Calls over the next 30 months, across five distinct water basins: Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, Baltic Sea, Danube and Rhine River. 7 Country Hubs will be guiding schools in the submission process and provide a Blue Curriculum to teachers, open-schooling opportunities, along with a platform to share their activities and engage with stakeholders. The marine mammal community can actively contribute to at least three directions: providing information for the Blue Curriculum to teachers; participate as evaluators in the calls for project proposals; and co-develop projects that can contribute to the well-being of marine mammals and marine and riverine ecosystems. Overall, the SHORE project will help communities to become aware of the water environment around them and its concrete role in their life. This will increase consideration of the local ecosystems to navigate solutions to future challenges in conservation.